

Assessment of Bilirubin, Alkaline Phosphatase, Aspartate and Alanine Transaminases of Domestic Gas Factory Workers

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Abstract

Gasoline station workers are regularly exposed to many hazardous toxins vapors which can cause abnormal alterations in the functioning of many vital organs and they are associated with increased risk of liver dysfunction. This study was carried out to evaluate the Alkaline phosphatase (ALP), Aspartate Aminotransferase (AST), Alanine aminotransferase (ALT) and Bilirubin in domestic cooking gas factory workers in Benin City, Edo State. ALT, AST and ALP were determined enzymatically, while bilirubin was determined using Chemical Pathology semi-autoanalyzer. Statistical analysis was done using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) and the student's t-test. Significant difference was accepted at $p < 0.05$. The results presented in mean \pm standard deviation showed that the total bilirubin (mg/dl) of the subjects and control group was 1.12 ± 0.33 and 0.52 ± 0.18 , conjugated bilirubin (mg/dl) was 0.44 ± 0.12 and 0.28 ± 0.13 , AST (U/L) was 10.33 ± 2.35 and 6.97 ± 2.14 , ALT (U/L) was 8.43 ± 2.37 and 5.50 ± 2.05 , while ALP (U/L) was 74.83 ± 19.51 and 37.37 ± 17.23 respectively. Total bilirubin, conjugated bilirubin, AST, ALT and

More Information

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Factory Workers, Gas, Alkaline, Phosphatase, Aspartate, Alanine, Transaminases, Bilirubin.

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ALP were significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) in domestic gas factory workers compared with control group. The total bilirubin (mg/dl) of male and female subjects was 1.25 ± 0.36 and 0.97 ± 0.15 , conjugated bilirubin (mg/dl) was 0.45 ± 0.11 and 0.41 ± 0.12 , AST (U/L) was 10.83 ± 2.33 and 9.33 ± 1.92 , ALT (U/L) was 8.79 ± 2.32 and 7.58 ± 2.10 , while ALP (U/L) was 79.91 ± 17.56 and 64.17 ± 19.61 respectively. The total bilirubin (mg/dl) of domestic gas factory workers who have worked for less than 1 year, between 1 – 5 years and for more than 5 years was 0.94 ± 0.22 , 1.14 ± 0.25 and 1.54 ± 0.24 , conjugated bilirubin (mg/dl) was 0.38 ± 0.09 , 0.43 ± 0.09 and 0.57 ± 0.08 , AST (U/L) was 8.43 ± 1.16 , 10.50 ± 1.60 and 12.91 ± 1.81 , ALT (U/L) was 6.50 ± 1.95 , 8.79 ± 1.42 and 10.45 ± 1.81 , while ALP (U/L) was 57.71 ± 16.73 , 78.28 ± 10.40 and 93.55 ± 11.04 respectively. The study concludes that exposure to gasoline by domestic gas factory workers showed increase liver function test parameters. This study observed that the domestic gas factory workers are at risk of developing biochemical alterations in the hepatic enzymes and liver function tests. Long term exposure to gasoline should be monitored, thus calling for collaboration between the health workers and gas factory management to ensure frequent monitoring of their workers health.

Introduction

Liquefied petroleum gas (LPG) commonly called domestic cooking gas is a fuel gas which contains a flammable mixture of hydrocarbon gases, specifically propane, propylene, butylene, isobutane and n-butane [1, 2]. LPG is used as a fuel gas in heating appliances, cooking equipment, and vehicles. It is increasingly used as an aerosol propellant and a refrigerant, replacing chlorofluorocarbons in an effort to reduce damage to the ozone layer. When specifically used as a vehicle fuel, it is often referred to as autogas or even just as gas [3]. Varieties of LPG that are bought and sold include mixes that are mostly propane (C_3H_8), mostly butane (C_4H_{10}), and, most commonly mixes including both propane and butane. Propylene, butylenes and various other hydrocarbons are usually also present in small concentrations such as C_2H_6 , CH_4 , and C_3H_8 . A powerful odorant, ethanethiol, is added so that leaks can be detected easily [4].

LPG is prepared by refining petroleum or "wet" natural gas, and is almost entirely derived from fossil fuel sources, being manufactured during the refining of petroleum (crude oil), or extracted from petroleum or natural gas streams as they emerge from the ground [5]. Exposure to LPG is mainly by inhalation or by eye and skin contact. Inhaling LPG vapor at high concentration even for a short time can cause asphyxiation, seizures, comas, heart problems and death. Inhalation of LPG may cause drowsiness or dizziness and respiratory irritation (cough, sneezing, headache, nose and throat pain). Long-term exposure may lead to central nervous system damage, nosebleeds, rhinitis, oral/nasal ulcerations, conjunctivitis, weight loss and fatigue. Eye and skin irritation may occur due to contact with LPG. LPG released under pressure can cause frostbite burn due to rapid temperature decrease [3].

The plasma enzymes including Alkaline Phosphatase (ALP), Aspartate Aminotransferase (AST) and Alanine Aminotransferase (ALT) together with the bilirubin form part of the major functional markers of the liver [6]. The most frequent laboratory tests for detecting

liver diseases are serum aminotransferases assays, which comprise aspartate aminotransferase (AST) and alanine aminotransferase (ALT). They are great indicators of hepatocellular damage [7]. AST is mainly present in the heart, liver, skeletal muscles, kidney, brain, pancreas, lungs, white blood cells and red blood cells [8], whereas ALT is found in serum and in many body tissues, but is more frequently linked to the liver [9]. Because ALT is mostly found in the cytosol of liver cells and is present in low concentrations elsewhere, it is believed to be more selective for hepatic damage [8]. Although AST has both mitochondrial (80% of total activity) and cytosolic (20%) components, it is less sensitive and selective for the liver [7]. While AST catalyzes the interconversion of aspartate and α -ketoglutarate to oxaloacetate and glutamate, ALT catalyzes the transfer of an amino group from alanine to α -ketoglutarate [10]. The results of this reversible transamination process are pyruvate and glutamate [10].

Several constituents of the LPG products have been found to be hazardous including benzene, xylene and toluene with benzene being the most hazardous [11]. These hazardous effects include the onset of anaemia and cancer which is more evident in individuals with prolonged exposure [12]. It is obvious that LPG attendants in filling stations, drivers of gasoline trucks, service station attendants and refinery workers are more susceptible to the harms of LPG due to chronic work-related exposure [13]. LPG is readily available in the atmosphere any time due to the fact that they are volatile and this is most common in LPG plant stations and depots [14]. The deleterious effects of exposure to LPG depend largely on the chemicals that constitute LPG such as benzene and lead [13]. Inhalation of LPG vapors even in small amounts have been reported to cause dizziness, headaches, nose and throat irritation, breathing difficulties, confusion, vomiting, allergic and skin reaction such as rash and redness [13].

Furthermore, a more serious health implication of LPG is related to the alteration of the haemopoietic system with bone marrow depression [15]. Diseases that are

related to occupation in LPG plant stations have been reported over the years and affect workers in several ways, and this poses a major threat to their health and wellbeing. There is growing concern over the use of LPG among individuals who constantly inhale this substance with a reported significant higher disease burden [16]. These occupational health hazards have significantly increased mostly in industrialized and developing countries [17]. Although many enzymes have been identified as useful in the assessment of liver function, the most clinically useful include the alanine aminotransferase (ALT), aspartate aminotransferase (AST), alkaline phosphatase (ALP) and bilirubin. However, there are limited studies on the effects of LPG exposure on liver function parameters, which necessitate the reason for this study.

Materials and Methods

Study Area

This study was carried out in Benin City, Edo State. Edo State is an inland state in western Nigeria. It is bounded in the north and east by Kogi State, in the south by Delta State and in the west by Ondo State. English is the official language of the state. The major tribal languages spoken in the state are Igarra, Edo, Esan and Okpamheri. Edo State is the home to several ethnicities; among them are Edo, Okpe, Esan, Afemai, Ora, Akoko-Edo, Igbanke, Emai and Ijaw. The 2014 population of Edo State was estimated to be 6 million. Benin City is the capital of Edo State with a population of 2,147,188. It is a city approximately 25 miles (40km) north of the Benin River. It is situated 200 miles (320km) by road east of Lagos. Benin is the centre of Nigeria's rubber industry, processing palm nuts for oil is also an important traditional industry.

Study Design

The study was a cross-sectional comparative study conducted on domestic gas factory workers in Benin City, Edo State, Nigeria between January and May, 2024 in which liver function test parameters in domestic gas factory workers were compared with apparently healthy individuals (control group). Male and female subjects of comparative age groups were recruited for this study. Questionnaires were used to collect the information on age, duration of work in gas factory and general health status.

Study Population

A total of seventy (70) subjects between the ages of 20-60 years were recruited for this study which consist of forty (40) domestic gas factory workers and thirty (30) individuals who are not domestic gas factory workers (controls).

Ethical Approval and Informed Consent

Ethical approval for the collection of samples was obtained from the Ethics and Review Committee, Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma. Informed consent

was sought from each subject who participated in the study before the collection of samples.

Sample Size

The number of samples studied was guided by the upper limit required, and gave 95% level of confidence at a prevalence of 5.6% pilot study, using the precise prevalence formula:

$$N = \frac{z^2 pg}{d^2} \quad (1)$$

Where; N= the desired sample size (when population is greater than 10,000)

z = is a constant given as 1.96 (or more simply at 2.0) which corresponds to the 95% confidence level.

p = prevalence (4.5%)

q = 1.0 – p

d = acceptable error (5%)

$$N = \frac{(1.96)^2 \cdot 0.045 \cdot (1-0.045)}{(0.05)^2} = \frac{3.8416 \cdot 0.045 \cdot 0.955}{0.0025} = 66$$

To make up for the sampling error or drop outs, a total of seventy (70) samples was collected and used for the research comprising of forty domestic gas factory workers (subjects) and thirty (30) controls.

Inclusion Criteria

Apparently healthy domestic gas factory workers with no history of smoking, acute infection, systemic illness underlying and any other underlining illness or symptoms who gave their consent were included in this study.

Exclusion Criteria

Subjects who are not within 18 – 45 years, have underlying illness or symptoms and those who did not give their consent were excluded from the study.

Sample Collection

For each participant, about four (4) ml of blood was collected into plain bottles by venipuncture. They were labeled and allowed to clot. The serum was separated by centrifugation. The serum was carefully withdrawn into a pre-labeled tube. Specimens not tested immediately were stored at –20°C.

Analytical Methods

Estimation of Alanine Aminotransferase (ALT)

The ALT activity in the sample was determined using the method described by Rietman and Frankel, [18].

Principle: ALT catalyses the transfer of amino group from alanine to alpha oxoglutarate forming L-glutamate and pyruvate. The pyruvate reacts with 2, 4-dinitrophenyl hydrazine which in an alkaline medium gives a reddish brown colour which is measured spectrophotometrically at 546nm wavelength. The intensity of the colour is directly proportional to the enzyme activity.

Procedure

About 0.5ml of buffer ALT substrate solution was added in test tubes labeled test and blank and incubated at 37°C for 5 minutes. 0.1ml of plasma was added to test and mixed thoroughly. It was incubated for 30 mins. 0.5ml of 2, 4-dinitrophenyl hydrazine (DNPH) was added to each test tube (test and blank). All tubes were mixed well and allowed to stand at room temperature for 20 mins. 5.0ml of 0.4N sodium hydroxide (NaOH) was added to each of the test tube and allowed to stand at room temperature for 5 mins. The absorbance was read at 546nm. The ALT activity was obtained from the calibration curve.

Estimation of Aspartate Aminotransferase (AST)

The AST activity in the sample was determined using the method described by Rietman and Frankel [18].

Principle: AST catalyses the transfer of an amino group from aspartate to alpha oxoglutarate forming L-glutamate and oxaloacetate which reacts with 2, 4-dinitrophenyl hydrazine which in an alkaline medium gives a reddish brown colour which is measured spectrophotometrically at 546nm wavelength. The intensity of the colour is directly proportional to the enzyme activity.

Procedure

About 0.5ml of buffer AST substrate solution was added in test tubes labeled test and blank and incubated in water bath at 37°C for 5 minutes. 0.1ml of plasma was added to test and mixed thoroughly. It was incubated for 30 mins. 0.5ml of 2, 4-dinitrophenyl hydrazine (DNPH) was added to each test tube (test and blank). 0.1ml of plasma was added to each test blank containing 0.5ml of buffered substrate and this was used as sample blank. All tubes were mixed well and allowed to stand at room temperature for 20 mins. 5.0ml of 0.4N sodium hydroxide (NaOH) was added to each of the test tube and allowed to stand at room temperature for 5 mins. The absorbance was read at 546nm. The AST activity was obtained from the calibration curve.

Estimation of Alkaline Phosphatase [19]

Principle: Serum ALP hydrolyzes phenyl phosphate into phenol and disodium hydrogen phosphate at pH 10.0. The phenol so formed reacts with 4-Aminoantipyrine in alkaline medium in presence of oxidizing agent Potassium ferricyanide to form a red colored complex whose absorbance is proportional to the enzyme activity.

Bilirubin Estimation

The total and conjugated bilirubin were estimated using the method described by Jendrassik and Grof, [20]

Principle: Bilirubin reacts with diazotized sulfanilic acid to form an azo dye which is red in neutral and blue in alkaline solutions. Whereas the water-soluble bilirubin glucuronides react “directly”, the free “indirect” bilirubin reacts only in the presence of an accelerator. The total bilirubin in serum or plasma is determined using the method of Jendrassik and Gróf [20] by coupling with diazotized sulfanilic acid after the addition of caffeine, sodium benzoate and sodium acetate. A blue azobilirubin is formed in alkaline Fehling’s solution II. This blue compound can also be determined selectively in the presence of yellow by-products (green mixed coloration) by photometry at 578 nm. Direct bilirubin is measured as the red azo dye at 546 nm using the method of Schellong and Wende [21] without the addition of alkali. Indirect bilirubin is calculated from the difference between the total and direct bilirubin

Statistical Analysis

All results were presented in tables and chart as mean ± standard deviation. Statistical analysis was done using one way analysis of variance (ANOVA) and Student’s t-test using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 21.0. A p-values <0.05 was considered significant.

Results

Table 1 showed the liver function test parameters of domestic gas factory workers compared with control group. The results presented in mean ± standard deviation showed that the total bilirubin (mg/dl) in mean ± standard deviation of the subjects and control group was 1.12±0.33 and 0.52±0.18, conjugated bilirubin (mg/dl) was 0.44±0.12 and 0.28±0.13, AST (U/L) was 10.33±2.35 and 6.97±2.14, ALT (U/L) was 8.43±2.37 and 5.50±2.05, while ALP (U/L) was 74.83±19.51 and 37.37±17.23 respectively. Total bilirubin, conjugated bilirubin, AST, ALT and ALP were significantly higher (p<0.05) in domestic gas factory workers compared with control group.

Table 1: Liver Function Test Parameters of Domestic Gas Factory Workers Compared with Control

Parameters	Subjects (Mean ± SD) (n = 40)	Controls (Mean ± SD) (n = 30)	t-value	p-value
TB (mg/dl)	1.12±0.33	0.52±0.18	8.954	0.000
CB (mg/dl)	0.44±0.12	0.28±0.13	4.782	0.000
AST (U/L)	10.33±2.35	6.97±2.14	5.578	0.000
ALT (U/L)	8.43±2.37	5.50±2.05	4.639	0.000
ALP (U/L)	74.83±19.51	37.37±17.23	7.733	0.000

Note: *Values are significant at p<0.05

Keys: TB – Total bilirubin, CB – Conjugated bilirubin; ALP – Alkaline Phosphatase; AST – Aspartate Aminotransferase; ALT – Alanine Aminotransferase; n – Sample size

Table 2 showed the liver function test parameters of domestic gas factory workers with respect to gender. The results presented in mean ± standard deviation showed that the total bilirubin (mg/dl) in mean ± standard deviation of male and female subjects was 1.25±0.36 and 0.97±0.15, conjugated bilirubin (mg/dl) was 0.45±0.11 and 0.41±0.12, AST (U/L) was 10.83±2.33 and 9.33±1.92, ALT (U/L) was 8.79±2.32 and

7.58±2.10, while ALP (U/L) was 79.91±17.56 and 64.17±19.61 respectively. Total bilirubin, AST and ALP were significantly higher (p<0.05) in male domestic gas factory workers compared with female domestic gas factory workers. Similarly, conjugated bilirubin and ALT were higher in male subjects compared with female subjects; however the difference was not statistically significant.

Table 2: Liver Function Test Parameters of Domestic Gas Factory Workers with Respect to Gender

Parameters	Male subjects (Mean ± SD) (n = 12)	Female subjects (Mean ± SD) (n = 28)	t-value	p-value
TB (mg/dl)	1.25±0.36	0.97±0.15	4.071	0.000*
CB (mg/dl)	0.45±0.11	0.41±0.12	1.252	0.223
AST (U/L)	10.83±2.33	9.33±1.92	2.376	0.026*
ALT (U/L)	8.79±2.32	7.58±2.10	1.998	0.058
ALP (U/L)	79.91±17.56	64.17±19.61	3.291	0.003*

Note: *Values are significant at p<0.05

Keys: TB – Total bilirubin, CB – Conjugated bilirubin; ALP – Alkaline Phosphatase; AST – Aspartate Aminotransferase; ALT – Alanine Aminotransferase; n – Sample size

Table 3 showed the liver function test parameters of domestic gas factory workers with respect to age. The results obtained showed that the mean ± SD of total bilirubin (mg/dl) in age group 18–25 years, 26–30 years and 31–45 years was 0.94±0.21, 1.18±0.34 and 1.41±0.24, conjugated bilirubin (mg/dl) was 0.38±0.09, 0.46±0.13 and 0.51±0.08, AST (U/L) was 8.50±1.24, 10.50±2.19 and 11.85±2.10, ALT (U/L) was 7.08±2.19,

8.33±2.31 and 9.50±2.06, while ALP (U/L) was 59.17±19.01, 75.58±16.30 and 87.71±12.07 respectively. Total bilirubin, conjugated bilirubin, AST, ALT and ALP was significantly higher (p<0.05) in age group 31-45 years compared to age group 18-25 years. There was significant increase (p<0.05) in liver function test parameters with respect to age.

Table 3: Liver Function Test Parameters of Domestic Gas Factory Workers with Respect to Age

Parameters	18–25 years Mean ± SD	26–30 years Mean ± SD	31–45 years Mean ± SD	F-value	p-value
TB (mg/dl)	0.94±0.21 ^a	1.18±0.34 ^a	1.41±0.24 ^b	4.732	0.000
CB (mg/dl)	0.38±0.09 ^a	0.46±0.13 ^b	0.51±0.08 ^b	3.646	0.003
AST (U/L)	8.50±1.24 ^a	10.50±2.19 ^b	11.85±2.10 ^b	4.238	0.001
ALT (U/L)	7.08±2.19 ^a	8.33±2.31 ^{ab}	9.50±2.06 ^b	2.305	0.038
ALP (U/L)	59.17±19.01 ^a	75.58±16.30 ^b	87.71±12.07 ^b	4.786	0.000

Note: *Values in a row with different superscript are significant at p<0.05.

Keys: TB – Total bilirubin, CB – Conjugated bilirubin; ALP – Alkaline Phosphatase; AST – Aspartate Aminotransferase; ALT – Alanine Aminotransferase; n – Sample size

Table 4 showed the liver function test parameters of domestic gas factory workers with respect to duration of work. The results obtained showed that the mean ± SD of total bilirubin (mg/dl) in domestic gas factory workers who have worked for less than 1 year, between 1 – 5 years and for more than 5 years was 0.94±0.22, 1.14±0.25 and 1.54±0.24, conjugated bilirubin (mg/dl) was 0.38±0.09, 0.43±0.09 and 0.57±0.08, AST (U/L) was 8.43±1.16, 10.50±1.60 and 12.91±1.81, ALT (U/L) was

6.50±1.95, 8.79±1.42 and 10.45±1.81, while ALP (U/L) was 57.71±16.73, 78.28±10.40 and 93.55±11.04 respectively. Total bilirubin, conjugated bilirubin, AST, ALT and ALP was significantly higher (p<0.05) in domestic gas factory workers who have worked for more than 5 years compared to those who have worked for less than one year. There was significant increase (p<0.05) in liver function test parameters with respect to duration of work.

Table 4: Liver Function Test Parameters of Domestic Gas Factory Workers with Respect to Duration of Work

Parameters	<1 year Mean ± SD	1–5 years Mean ± SD	>5 years Mean ± SD	F-value	p-value
TB (mg/dl)	0.94±0.22 ^a	1.14±0.25 ^b	1.54±0.24 ^c	4.079	0.001
CB (mg/dl)	0.38±0.09 ^a	0.43±0.09 ^b	0.57±0.08 ^c	4.282	0.001
AST (U/L)	8.43±1.16 ^a	10.50±1.60 ^b	12.91±1.81 ^c	6.118	0.000
ALT (U/L)	6.50±1.95 ^a	8.79±1.42 ^b	10.45±1.81 ^c	5.380	0.000
ALP (U/L)	57.71±16.73 ^a	78.28±10.40 ^b	93.55±11.04 ^c	7.610	0.000

Note: *Values in a row with different superscript are significant at p<0.05.

Keys: TB – Total bilirubin, CB – Conjugated bilirubin; ALP – Alkaline Phosphatase; AST – Aspartate Aminotransferase; ALT – Alanine Aminotransferase; n – Sample size

Table 5 showed the relationship between Liver function test parameters among domestic gas factory workers using Pearson correlation. From the results obtained, there was a significant positive correlation between TB and CB (p=0.000), between TB and AST (p=0.000), between TB and ALT (p=0.025) and between TB and ALP (p=0.000) respectively among domestic gas factory workers. There was a significant positive correlation between CB and AST (p=0.000), between CB and ALT

(p=0.001) and between CB and ALP (p=0.000) respectively among domestic gas factory workers. There was a significant positive correlation between AST and ALT (p=0.000) and between AST and ALP (p=0.000) respectively among domestic gas factory workers. There was a significant positive correlation between ALT and ALP (p=0.001) among domestic gas factory workers.

Table 5: Relationship between Liver Function Test Parameters among Domestic Gas Factory Workers Using Pearson Correlation

		TB	CB	AST	ALT	ALP
TB	Pearson Correlation		0.762**	0.626**	0.353*	0.711**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.000	0.000	0.025	0.000
	N		40	40	40	40
CB	Pearson Correlation	0.762**		0.669**	0.505**	0.530**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000		0.000	0.001	0.000
	N	40		40	40	40
AST	Pearson Correlation	0.626**	0.669**		0.851**	0.693**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000		0.000	0.000
	N	40	40		40	40
ALT	Pearson Correlation	0.353*	0.505**	0.851**		.503**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.025	0.001	0.000		.001
	N	40	40	40		40
ALP	Pearson Correlation	0.711**	0.530**	0.693**	0.503**	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.001	
	N	40	40	40	40	

Note: **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed); *. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Discussion

Gasoline station workers are regularly exposed to many hazardous toxins vapors. Some of these vapors are gasoline, kerosene, and diesel, among the most risky toxin is benzene fume. Which can cause abnormal alterations in the functioning of many vital organs and they are associated with increased risk of renal and liver dysfunction [22]. This study was carried out to determine the liver function test parameters of domestic gas factory workers in Benin City, Edo State, Nigeria.

Serum ALT and AST were significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) in domestic gas factory workers than controls study participants. The significantly increase in ALT and AST is in line with other studies conducted in Egypt [23], Nigeria [24 - 26], Turkey [27], Sudan [28], Palestine [22], India [29] and Brazil [30]. This observation may be due to the fact that hydrocarbons are a major component of petroleum products that are metabolized in the liver by CYP450 2E1 oxidative pathways, which contribute to the production of free radicals and quinone metabolites such as phenol, hydroquinone, benzoquinone; 1,2,4 benzenetriol [7]. These free radicals and toxic metabolites cause lipid peroxidation and damage of hepatic cell membrane, causing the release of liver enzymes in the circulation [31]. The study of Dioka *et al.* [32] also revealed that while ALT and AST activities were elevated in occupationally exposed artisans to gasoline than in controls, ALP activity was significantly lower in the exposed subjects than in controls. Waldman & Borman [33] had earlier reported similar findings of increased serum ALT and AST activities among domestic gas factory workers.

The ALP level was significantly higher in domestic gas factory workers compared with controls. This result is in line with previous studies conducted in Nigeria [25, 26, 34]. ALP is an enzyme mostly found in the cells lining the biliary ducts of the liver. If there is an obstruction in the bile duct, ALP may leak into blood stream and ALP levels in plasma will rise [35]. ALP is also present in placental tissue and in growing children for bone remodeling [22]. All the study participants considered for this study are adult; therefore, significantly higher levels of ALP in domestic gas factory workers may indicate presence of bile duct obstruction. Similar levels of total bilirubin in petrol attendants and controls are an indication that hemolysis or liver damage may occur in the petrol attendants.

Although serum electrophoresis was not done in this study to distinguish the isoenzyme fractions of the total ALP (elevated in domestic gas factory workers over their control peers) and possibly establish or rule out other conditions including presence of tumours or carcinomas, it is believed that a reasonable pointer has been shown as to the possible conditions indicated by Anicteric significant rise in alkaline phosphatase among

domestic gas factory workers. Based on these submissions, it could be said that part of the health risks associated with occupational exposures in the Oil and Gas industry are among others, the possible development of bone diseases with increased osteoblastic activity, liver diseases with involvement of the biliary tracts, toxic hepatitis, liver cirrhosis, malignancies of various body sites including bronchial carcinoma, hepatoma and leukaemia, etc. In fact, apart from the various degrees of accidents and injuries previously reported among these same petroleum refining and distribution workers [36], results also indicated that some of the above highlighted conditions including liver diseases, made reckonable contributions to the morbidities and mortalities recorded in this industry, thus suggesting the presence of organs/systems toxic agents in this work environment [37].

In this study, Total bilirubin, conjugated bilirubin were significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) in domestic gas factory workers compared to control subjects. This result is in agreement with previous reports who reported similar results [24 - 26]. Abnormal liver functions with neurological symptoms were reported in individuals who had accidental inhalation of natural gas containing propane and butane [38]. In addition, there are reports on the hepatotoxic effect of kerosene and petrol contaminated diets in Wistar albino rats [39] and this collaborates with the findings in this study.

There was significant increase ($p < 0.05$) in liver function test parameters (AST, ALT, ALP, total bilirubin and conjugated bilirubin) with respect to duration of work. Total bilirubin, conjugated bilirubin, AST, ALT and ALP was significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) in domestic gas factory workers who have worked for more than 5 years compared to those who have worked for less than one year. Our result is in agreement with the results obtained from other settings for LPG or natural gas exposures. Hu *et al.* [40] showed that long-term exposure to coke oven emissions increased the risk of liver dysfunction, while Chen *et al.* [41] and Wu *et al.* [42] explored the dose-response relationship between exposure to natural gas emissions in coke oven workers and the elevation of some serum liver enzymes, and reported a significant elevation of some liver enzymes in these workers that may have been related to their exposure to natural gas.

AST is present in high concentration in cells of cardiac and skeletal muscles, liver, kidney and erythrocytes. Thus, damage to any of these tissues may increase plasma AST levels. In like manner, ALT is present in high concentrations in liver and to a lesser extent in skeletal muscle, kidney and heart [43]. Marked increase of the enzymes (10 to 100 times the upper limit of adult reference range) may be caused by circulatory failure with 'shock' and hypoxia, myocardial infarction

(particularly for AST) and acute viral or toxic hepatitis. Given the multiple locations of these enzymes, i.e. their presence in many tissues, changes in their plasma activities may reflect damage to any of those tissues, thus allowing room for a needful differential diagnosis. Hence, a careful evaluation of the variously highlighted conditions above is relevant alongside consideration of the plasma bilirubin concentrations [6, 44].

In this study, there was significant increase ($p < 0.05$) in liver function test parameters with respect to age. Total bilirubin, AST and ALP were significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) in male domestic gas factory workers compared with female domestic gas factory workers. Similarly, conjugated bilirubin and ALT were higher in male subjects compared with female subjects; however, the difference was not statistically significant. These findings are in agreement with the earlier report [24 – 26, 44]. These findings showed that male subjects and older domestic gas factory workers were more at risk of developing biochemical alterations in the liver function test parameters. Furthermore, the fact that there was consistently significant increase in values of liver enzymes clearly points to the existence of certain conditions among the domestic gas factory workers that was not obtained among the non-domestic gas factory workers [2, 45].

The study revealed that though the levels of the assayed hepatic biochemical markers were still within the parametric reference ranges as at the time of this study, however, relative to the non-domestic gas workers that served as the control group, changes observed in the biochemical markers among the domestic gas factory workers suggested that petroleum and gas refining and distribution work environment is furnished with some hepatotoxic substances and that anicteric hepatotoxicity is a potential health effect of long term occupational exposures in the petroleum and gas refining and distribution industry in Nigeria, hence, long-serving staff might be victims of anicteric toxic hepatitis.

Conclusion

The study concludes that exposure to gasoline by domestic gas factory workers showed increase liver function test parameters. This study observed that the domestic gas factory workers are at risk of developing biochemical alterations in the hepatic enzymes and liver function tests. The liver function test parameters (total bilirubin, conjugated bilirubin, AST, ALT and ALP) were significantly increased ($p < 0.05$) in male subjects, older domestic gas factory workers and those who have been working for in domestic gas factory for over 5 years compared with control group. There should be the introduction of initial medical or laboratory testing for gas station attendants before being hired to their jobs to check their fitness and suitability for duties at gas stations and regular monitoring of their health

while on the job. The availability and use of Personal Protective Equipments (PPE) at work to minimize workplace gas exposure should be encouraged. Further longer-term perspective studies of domestic gas workers will help to get a more comprehensive picture of long term effects of gas exposure.

Availability of Data and Materials

The authors declare consent for all available data present in this study.

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Competing Interests

The authors declare no conflicts of interest

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